

Development of a Serious Game for Mental Health: Requirements Analysis via the Delphi Method

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Abstract— Mental health disorders represent a significant global challenge, particularly among young adults. While serious games are emerging as a promising complementary tool for mental health support, their efficacy hinges on a design that deeply integrates the needs of both patients and clinicians. This study aims to identify and synthesize the essential requirements for a serious game designed to support young adults with anxiety and/or depression, using the Delphi method. A qualitative and exploratory study was conducted with 17 participants (10 patients diagnosed with anxiety and/or depression and seven mental health professionals). Data on desired features, mechanics, and ethical considerations were collected via structured online questionnaires and analyzed using Thematic Content Analysis. The analysis revealed convergence between the two groups on several requirements, including a therapeutic core gameplay loop, a gamified and clinically relevant progress dashboard, a positive reinforcement system, and the importance of a validated, ethical, and safe environment that aligns with patients' need for a welcoming, non-judgmental space. These findings provide actionable guidelines for the second Delphi round, aimed at achieving quantitative consensus for the subsequent design of the serious game.

Keywords — *Serious Games, Mental Health, Digital Health, Delphi Method, User-Centered Design.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Mental health disorders are one of the greatest global challenges, affecting millions of people across different age groups and social contexts. Even before the COVID-19 pandemic, the World Health Organization (WHO) estimated that one in eight people in the world lived with a mental condition [1]. However, the pandemic crisis drastically aggravated this scenario, with the WHO itself calculating that the global prevalence of anxiety and depression increased 25% in the first year of pandemic alone [2]. This impact was especially pronounced among young adults and university students, whose academic and social routines can generate high levels of stress and emotional burden [3]. Recent

studies show that, two years after the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, more than one in three students reported clinically relevant symptoms of depression and nearly one third presented with anxiety symptoms [4]. A global meta-analysis also confirmed that post-secondary students experienced significantly higher levels of depression and anxiety during the pandemic, highlighting the vulnerability of this group [5].

In response to this concerning scenario, there has been a growing use of complementary technological strategies to traditional care, notably meditation apps, teletherapy platforms, and, more recently, serious games aimed at promoting mental health [6][7]. Serious games can combine playful and narrative elements with health, education, or professional training objectives, creating interactive environments where the user, through constant challenges and feedback, can develop cognitive, emotional, and behavioral skills [7][8].

For such tools to be truly effective in practice, it is essential to listen to both those living with these disorders and the professionals who support them, ensuring that clinical, motivational and technical requirements are guaranteed from the conception phase [9][10]. A consolidated approach to eliciting consensus in multidisciplinary settings is the Delphi method, which allows consensus building through structured questionnaire rounds [11]. Originally developed by RAND Corporation in the 1950s, the Delphi method is characterized by anonymity of responses, controlled feedback, and statistical aggregation of group opinion [12]. Each round has specific goals: The first typically focuses on collecting qualitative insights through open-ended questions, while subsequent rounds aim at quantifying agreement and prioritizing items, gradually moving toward a consensus [13] [14]. This iterative process makes the Delphi method particularly useful in health-related research such as this, where the perspectives of both professionals and patients can be essential to establish requirements and best practices.

In this context, this study aims to present the results of the first round of the Delphi method, conducted with patients and mental health professionals, with the purpose of identifying essential requirements for the development of a serious game

II. METHODOLOGY

This study is a qualitative, exploratory, and descriptive research, which utilized the Delphi technique in its first round with the objective of gathering requirements from multiple points of view. The research involved 17 adult volunteers of various ages, comprising 10 patients diagnosed with anxiety and/or depression and seven mental health professionals, such as psychologists and psychiatrists, who reported experience in treating patients with these disorders. The study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee under number 83857524.7.0000.5152.

For data collection, an online form developed on the Google Forms platform was used. For patients, the form contained 12 questions, with six being open-ended and six being multiple-choice/Likert scale. For professionals, the form contained 15 questions, with 11 being open-ended and four being multiple-choice/Likert scale. Both versions covered various topics such as challenges, success factors, mechanic preferences, metrics, and personalization.

Data collection procedures took place between April 22 and May 12, 2025. Participants were selected through non-probabilistic convenience sampling, using the snowball sampling technique. A link to the online form was distributed in academic community groups and on social media platforms, such as WhatsApp.

On the initial page of the form, participants were provided with detailed information about the research objectives, the voluntary nature of their participation, and the guarantee of total anonymity and data confidentiality. Only after giving their consent was the participant directed to the questionnaire.

For the analysis of the open-ended responses, which constitute the core of this first Delphi round, Thematic Content Analysis was employed, following the guidelines of Laurence Bardin [15]. The process was conducted by three researchers from the study team, who independently coded the material and then discussed their categorizations to reach consensus. The analysis followed three chronological stages:

- **Pre-analysis:** A preliminary reading of all collected material to become familiar with the content. Subsequently, the material was organized, separating the responses by group (patients and professionals) to facilitate comparative analysis.
- **Material Exploration:** In this phase, the responses of each group were read multiple times to define units of meaning (coding). Similar units of meaning were grouped by semantic proximity, giving rise to emerging thematic categories.
- **Treatment of Results and Interpretation:** The thematic categories were consolidated and refined. The final objective of this analysis was to condense the vast qualitative material into a structured list of initial requirements, which will be submitted for evaluation and prioritization in the second round of the Delphi study.

TABLE 1. Thematic categories identified in patients' responses.

Thematic Category	Brief Description	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Evidence based tools	Mindfulness, breathing exercises, relaxing sensory atmosphere, and game mechanics that promote focus and distraction.	8 out of 10	80%
Engagement through positive reinforcement	Need for tangible feedback that marks progress (achievements, levels) along with emotional validation to boost self-esteem (praise, motivational messages).	9 out of 10	90%
Progress visualization and perceived effectiveness	Motivation for continued use is linked to the ability to visualize emotional progress and perceive real improvement in anxiety and well-being.	9 out of 10	90%
Safe and welcoming environment	Need for a nonjudgmental space with a calming aesthetic and positive language.	4 out of 9	44%
Limitations and precautions	Avoid screen overuse and potential emotional triggers.	3 out of 10	30%

A. Patients' perspective

The analysis of the responses from the 10 participants in the patient group revealed a strong emphasis on emotional, usability, and motivational aspects. Table 1 presents the most frequent thematic categories and the number of participants who mentioned them.

TABLE 2. Thematic categories identified in professionals' responses.

Thematic Category	Brief Description	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Ethical validation and boundaries	Emphasis on the need for validated content. Clear statement that the game does not replace therapy.	7 out of 7	100%
Interactive psychoeducation	The game can serve as a tool to teach and apply psychological concepts and techniques (e.g., CBT).	5 out of 7	71.43%
Integration with therapy	The game has potential to collect data (e.g., journaling, mood) and reinforce tasks between sessions.	5 out of 7	71.43%
Focus on practical skills	The game should help train coping, communication, and emotional regulation skills.	4 out of 7	57.14%
Barriers to access and engagement in treatment	Acknowledgment that cost, time, and stigma are access barriers that the game could help mitigate.	4 out of 7	57.14%
Privacy, confidentiality, and data protection	Explicit concern with protecting patient information and ensuring the technical security of collected data.	4 out of 7	57.14%

TABLE 3. Convergent requirements considered important for the development of the serious game.

Essential Requirement	Origin and Justification	Reference Group(s)
1. Structure a Therapeutic Core Gameplay Loop	Aligns patients' demand for mindfulness mechanics and stage progression with professionals' perspective of gradual challenges within a reflective narrative.	Both
3. Develop a Positive Reinforcement System	Addresses patients' desire for achievements and validation messages, and professionals' recommendation for emotional feedback reinforcing self-efficacy and experience flow.	Both
4. Ensure an Ethical and Safe Environment	Based on unanimous demand from professionals to ensure privacy, confidentiality, and clear boundaries (not replacing therapy), supported by patients' concern over excessive use.	Both (Emphasis from Professionals)
5. Therapeutic Journal	Include mood, thought, and trigger tracking to promote self-awareness and therapy support. Suggested by patients and strongly endorsed by professionals as a bridge to therapy.	Both
6. Provide Crisis Management Tools	Although not a primary focus for professionals, this is an essential requirement for patients seeking quick access to breathing and mindfulness exercises for symptom relief.	Patients

B. Professional' perspective

The analysis of the responses of the seven participants in the professional group demonstrated a significant concern with the clinical foundation, ethics, and therapeutic purpose of the game. Table 2 summarizes these priorities.

C. Mutual requirements matrix

Taking into account the analysis of the perspectives of both patients and professionals, a matrix of the main requirements for the development of the serious game was created. Table 3 presents, in a synthesized manner, these requirements, highlighting the points of convergence between the participating groups and their justifications.

IV. DISCUSSION

The objective of this study was to identify, through a first round of the Delphi methodology, the essential requirements for the development of a serious game aimed at the mental health of young adults, combining the perspectives of patients and professionals in the field. The main finding of this round is the notable convergence between the analyzed perspectives. Despite originating from different viewpoints, such as lived experience and clinical practice, they point towards a tool that must be simultaneously engaging, therapeutic, and, above all, ethical and responsible.

The demand for a "Therapeutic Core Gameplay Loop" and a "Hybrid Progress Dashboard" (Table 3) reflects a dual need: the serious game must offer activities with a clinical basis, such as mindfulness and cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT), while providing the player with solid proof of their progress. Interestingly, this finding strongly corroborates the existing literature on participatory design. Such studies have long emphasized the importance of involving end-users, not just to ensure clinical validity, but to create tools that are genuinely useful and motivational in daily life [9][10].

Patients demonstrated a preference for gamified progress visualizations, such as bars and graphs, which aligns with the need for a comprehensive approach that satisfies the

player's desire for feedback while producing data that can be significant in a therapeutic context.

The creation of an "Ethical and Safe Environment", mentioned by professionals, along with the need for a welcoming space cited by patients, demonstrates that for mental health tools, trust is a prerequisite. Concerns about confidentiality, content validation, and clarity that the digital game does not replace therapy or medication reinforce the guidelines proposed by Mohr et al. [10], who warn of the need for clear ethical guidelines in the field of digital health. The requirement for a "Therapeutic Journal", a feature strongly endorsed by both groups, exemplifies a duality: it is a tool for self-knowledge for the patient while also being a potential communication bridge to therapy, provided that the data is treated with due confidentiality.

While professionals focused on long-term aspects, such as psychoeducation, patients indicated a need for support for rapid symptomatic relief. This complementary view suggests that a successful serious game should operate on two timelines: offering relief and comfort, while structuring and building long-term skills.

It is important to acknowledge the limitations of this study. As it is a qualitative study with non-probabilistic sampling, the results cannot be generalized to the entire population of patients and professionals. The sample size, 17 participants, although adequate for a first Delphi round, is limited. However, the objective of this phase was not statistical generalization, but rather the gathering of a diverse range of requirements, which was achieved.

V. CONCLUSION

This study successfully fulfilled its objective of identifying a robust set of initial requirements for the development of a serious game focused on mental health. The convergence between the perspectives of patients and professionals reinforces the feasibility of creating a tool that is both desired by its users and validated by clinicians. The six requirements that were identified will serve as the foundation for the questionnaire in the second round of the Delphi method, where participants will prioritize the importance of

each item to reach a quantitative consensus. This consensus will guide the subsequent phases of the project, including the actual development and implementation of the serious game, aimed at providing an effective and engaging mental health intervention.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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